

Skin Lesion Detection Using CNN

Ashwin S Pillai

*Department. of Computer Applications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
ashwinpillai2024a@mca.ajce.in*

Lisha Varghese

*Department.of ComputerApplications
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering,
Kanjirappally, India
lishavarghese@amaljyothi.ac.in*

Abstract— Skin lesions, such as growths, patches, and moles, can range in severity from benign to malignant, thus a precise diagnosis is essential. This research improves skin lesion identification with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) with the HAM10000 dataset. Preprocessing of pictures is done for consistency, and then CNN architecture design is done for feature extraction. Overfitting is avoided via data augmentation, and model performance is evaluated using assessment metrics like confusion matrices and accuracy. Real-time lesion classification is made possible by integration into a Flask web application, which makes diagnosis more accessible. By using this method, CNNs raise the diagnostic bar for dermatology and enhance patient outcomes and diagnostic capacity.

Keywords—Skin Lesion, CNN, Machine Learning,

Deep Learning.

I. INTRODUCTION

Skin lesions encompass various abnormalities on the skin's surface, including growths, patches, and moles. They range from benign to malignant, requiring precise diagnosis for appropriate treatment. Skin lesions are indicative of underlying conditions such as melanoma, basal cell carcinoma, and squamous cell carcinoma, each presenting distinct characteristics and risks. Accurate identification of skin lesions is essential for effective dermatological management and patient care.

Machine learning (ML) and deep learning have brought about significant advances in many different fields, including medical image analysis. Machine learning (ML) allows computers to learn from data and make predictions or judgments without being explicitly programmed. Deep learning, a subtype of machine learning, involves training multi-layer artificial neural networks to learn complex models and representations from data.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), a versatile class of deep learning models, are widely used in image classification applications. CNNs are designed to quickly process visual data by automatically learning hierarchical features from raw pixel values. This approach, powered by convolutional and pooling layers, allows CNN to capture low-level and high-level features such as edges, textures, object shapes, and patterns.

CNNs can be trained to effectively classify medical image using huge datasets of annotated images, which will help medical staff make better decisions. The HAM10000 dataset, containing high-quality images of various skin conditions, was used in this study to leverage the potential of CNN in classifying skin lesions. The potential for improving clinical decision-making processes through automated diagnosis systems is highlighted by the application of Convolutional Networks (CNNs) in the classification of medical pictures.

The CNN model achieves the ability to distinguish between different types of skin lesions through extensive training and optimization, enabling automated diagnosis and accelerating timely medical interventions.

The combination of CNN and machine learning in medical image analysis has enormous potential to improve patient outcomes and advance dermatology expertise.

i) Data quality: The performance of the model depends heavily on the reliability of the dataset in classifying skin lesions. For accurate prediction, consistent and high-quality images are needed for different skin conditions. Model output can be distorted due to inconsistencies or errors in image quality or labelling. Therefore, to maintain data integrity and minimize bias, meticulous attention to data collection, annotation, and preparation is essential.

ii) Model selection: Choosing the right machine learning algorithm is essential in the field of skin lesion classification. Medical image analysis can benefit greatly from the application of convolutional neural networks (CNN), but other techniques such as support vector machines (SVM) or decision trees can also be useful. The complexity of the data set, available computing power, and desired performance metrics are some of the factors that determine which model best fits the data.

iii) Overfitting: Overfitting can occur in the skin lesion classification task when the model remembers the training data instead of identifying meaningful patterns. Techniques such as dropout regularization, data augmentation, and cross-validation can be applied to combat overfitting. Additionally, evaluating the model's performance on recent data, such as another validation dataset, helps determine the level of generalization and protect against the model's tendency to overfit.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11184283](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11184283)

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering
Kanjirappally, Kottayam

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Alquran et al. in [1] conducted a study focusing on the importance of early identification of melanoma for effective treatment. Melanoma, the worst type of skin cancer, has a high risk of spreading to other parts of the body. To increase diagnostic accuracy, researchers have used non-invasive methods in medical computer vision and image processing. This process includes collecting a database of dermoscopy images, preprocessing them, thresholding them for segmentation, and extracting statistical features such as ABCD parameters and gray-level co-occurrence matrices (GLCM). They calculated the overall dermoscopy score and selected features using principal component analysis (PCA) Support vector machine was used in the classification process (SVM). The results of the study indicate that the proposed strategy is effective in accurately identifying melanoma, as evidenced by a remarkable classification accuracy of 92%.

Alwakid et al. in [2], focused on automatic skin cancer detection using deep learning (DL) algorithms in their research. Given the prevalence of skin cancer worldwide, early detection is essential to achieve better treatment outcomes. The work proposes a technique to accurately extract lesion regions using the success of industry-wide DL algorithms. The research methodology consists of several steps: segmenting the region of interest (ROI) of the entire image using a segmentation technique, which uses an enhanced super-resolution generative adversarial network (ESRGAN) to improve image quality and use data augmentation to address data gaps. To classify skin lesions, a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a modified version of ResNet-50 are used. All seven different types of skin cancer from the HAM10000 dataset were included in the study's unbalanced sample. The proposed CNN-based model performs better than other studies, achieving superior performance metrics, such as an F-score of 0.86 and accuracy, precision, and recall.

Dwivedi et al introduce their research in [3], propose a deep learning-based system for quick diagnosis of skin conditions. Skin disorders, which range from mild to severe, situational to genetic, and transient to persistent, present a challenge to patients and doctors due to their complexity and ambiguity. This underscores the need for precise detection technology to mitigate risks. The study employs suitable parameter selection and annotation strategies to the Fast R-CNN deep learning model. With an impressive accuracy of 90% and an error rate of 0.3, the proposed method holds potential in identifying specific skin conditions using predefined classifiers.

Sahu et al. present their research in [4], addressing the significant global health problem of skin diseases. The classification of dermatological diseases has improved through the use of several machine learning methods and technological advances. The aim of this work is to accurately classify different skin conditions using machine learning techniques. Using four different data mining techniques - Support Vector

Machine (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbor (KNN), Random Forest (RF) and Naive Bayes (NB) algorithms - the study presents an approach new approach. The voting mechanism is used to combine SVM, KNN, RF and NB into a composite model. Acne, skin allergies, nail fungus, hair loss, and normal skin are the five categories by which the overall model divides skin diseases. Surprisingly, the proposed ensemble model outperforms previous classification methods, with the best accuracy being 97.33%. This research provides promising results for medical diagnosis and treatment by improving the accuracy and efficiency of classification of skin conditions.

Acosta et al. present their research in [5], highlights the importance of early identification of melanoma, a common form of skin cancer. The key to reducing disease-related mortality is early diagnosis. Researchers propose an automated method using advanced techniques such as deep learning with convolutional neural networks (CNN) to identify melanoma from dermoscopic images. The proposed method consists of two steps: first, the region of interest in the dermoscopy image is automatically cropped using a mask- and region-based CNN method, then the lesions are classified as "benign" or "malignant" using the ResNet152 architecture. The challenge-related database presented at the 2017 International Symposium on Biomedical Imaging was used to train, validate, and test the model. With an increased accuracy of 3.66% and a balanced accuracy of 9.96% compared to the best results recorded for melanoma detection when meeting the challenge, the proposed model shows improvements Noticeable improvements in accuracy and precision balance on the test dataset.

III. MOTIVATION

For successful diagnosis and treatment, skin abnormalities must be identified accurately and quickly. However, because it relies heavily on subjective visual assessment, this task often proves difficult. The need for automated and accurate detection technology increases as skin disorders become more common and the burden on healthcare systems increases. The goal of this study was to develop a convolutional neural network (CNN) model capable of improving skin lesion classification using deep learning and image analysis. The goal of this project is to support dermatologists and improve patient outcomes by improving the speed and accuracy of diagnosis. The ultimate goal of this research is to improve patient care and dermatological diagnosis.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The methodical approach we used to create and train a convolutional neural network (CNN) model for skin lesion categorization is described in the methodology section. The main procedures for gathering data, preparing it, designing the model architecture, training it, and evaluating it are

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11184283](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11184283)

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

covered in this part. Our objective is to offer a thorough rundown of the steps we took to select the dataset, prepare the data, create the CNN model architecture, train the model, and evaluate its effectiveness.

A. Data Collection and Preparation: At this stage, we searched a wide range of medical libraries and dermatology databases extensively for pictures of skin lesions. The objective was to gather a varied dataset including a wide range of skin diseases and lesion kinds. To improve the model's ability to generalize to new data, we paid close attention to the caliber and variety of the photos gathered. We created a metadata CSV file to organize the dataset, which contains relevant information such as image filenames, associated diagnoses (dx), patient demographics, and lesion characteristics. Preprocessing access was made easier by linking each image's path to its corresponding entry in the metadata CSV file.

B. Data Preprocessing: In machine learning pipelines, data preparation is an essential step, particularly when working with image data. A number of preparation processes were conducted in order to get the dataset ready for model training:

Image Resizing and Normalization: To guarantee consistency in input dimensions throughout samples, every image in the dataset was scaled to a standard resolution of 64x64 pixels. In addition, to aid in convergence during model training, pixel values were standardized to a range of 0 to 1.

Label Encoding: The LabelEncoder tool from the sklearn.preprocessing module was used to convert categorical labels that represented various skin conditions into numerical values. To transform categorical data into a format that could be used to train machine learning models, this step was crucial.

Label Encoding: The LabelEncoder tool from the sklearn.preprocessing module was used to convert categorical labels that represented various skin conditions into numerical values. To transform categorical data into a format that could be used to train machine learning models, this step was crucial.

Train-Test Split: The train_test_split function from the sklearn.model_selection module was used to split the dataset into training and testing groups. This made it possible to evaluate the model's performance on hypothetical data, which aided in determining how well it might be generalized.

C. Model Architecture:

Using this platform, users can diagnose and treat skin lesions quickly and intelligently. In conclusion, this research contributes to improving the dermatological diagnostic process, thereby improving patient outcomes and streamlining healthcare delivery. For the purpose of classifying skin lesions, the convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture is essential for extracting relevant characteristics from input images. The layers of our CNN model were as follows:

Convolutional Layers: To extract hierarchical features from the input photos, three convolutional layers with increasing filter depths (64, 128, and 128) and kernel sizes (3x3) were used. Rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation functions were used after each convolutional layer to add non-linearity to the model.

MaxPooling Layers: To reduce computational complexity and support translation invariance, max-pooling layers with a pool size of (2x2) were applied after each convolutional layer.

Layer of Flattening: This layer prepared the 3D feature maps for input into the densely connected layers by converting them into a 1D vector.

Densely Connected Layers: To accomplish high-level feature learning and classification, two densely connected layers, each with 256 and 7 units, were added. Multi-class classification

was made possible by the last layer, which generated probabilities for each class using a softmax activation function.

D. Model Training: The CNN model that was created underwent training with the training dataset and optimization with the Adam optimizer. During training, we used data augmentation approaches to reduce overfitting and improve the model's capacity to generalize to new data. To be more precise, we added to the training dataset by applying random transformations such as rotation, shear, zoom, width and height shifting, and horizontal flipping. The validation dataset was used to track the model's performance during the training process, which lasted several epochs. Early stopping strategies, which stopped training when validation loss stopped improving, were used to prevent overfitting.

E. Model Evaluation: The testing dataset was used to evaluate the trained CNN model's performance in skin lesion categorization after training. To evaluate the model's efficacy in identifying skin lesions, we calculated a number of performance indicators, such as accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score.

V. BUILDMODEL

Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture specifically designed for skin lesion categorization is used in the model's construction. It consists of fully connected layers for classification, pooling layers for dimensionality reduction, and convolutional layers for feature extraction. The model is trained using supplemented data to improve generalization after compilation with suitable loss and optimization methods.

1) Import Relevant Packages: To commence, we import the Python libraries and frameworks [Fig 1] that are essential for data manipulation, model construction, and assessment. Packages like NumPy, pandas, scikit-learn, Keras, Flask, and Matplotlib are included in this.

```
import os
from glob import glob
from PIL import Image
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import LabelEncoder
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, confusion_matrix
from keras.models import Sequential
from keras.layers import Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Flatten, Dense
from keras.preprocessing.image import ImageDataGenerator
from flask import Flask, render_template, request
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

Fig 1. Imports

2) Data Loading and Preprocessing: The skin lesion dataset is then loaded from a CSV file that contains metadata. We preprocess the photos by encoding labels for categorization, standardizing pixel values, and scaling them to a standard resolution [Fig 2].

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11184283](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11184283)

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

```
# Read metadata CSV file
skin_df = pd.read_csv("C:/data/HAM10000/HAM10000_metadata.csv")

# Map image paths to 'path' column
image_path = {os.path.splitext(os.path.basename(x))[0]: x
               for x in glob(os.path.join('C:/data/HAM10000/', '*.jpg'))}
skin_df['path'] = skin_df['image_id'].map(image_path.get)
# Remove missing image paths
skin_df = skin_df.dropna(subset=['path'])

# Read and preprocess images
usage
def preprocess_image(img_path):
    img = Image.open(img_path)
    img = img.resize((64, 64)) # Resize images to a smaller resolution
    img = np.array(img) / 255.0 # Normalize pixel values
    return img
```

Fig 2. Preprocessing

Dataset: The collection consists of pictures of skin lesions and the labels that belong to them, describing the kind of lesion. Using scikit-learn's train_test_split method, it is split into training and testing sets.

3) Model Training: We use the Sequential API provided by Keras to create a CNN model architecture [Fig 3]. Convolutional layers and max-pooling layers are the order in which the model is built for feature extraction and dimensionality reduction. Upon assembling the model with suitable loss and optimization functions, we employ the training dataset to train it. Lastly, we store the trained model for usage in real-world applications or for later use.

```
# Split dataset into training and testing sets
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(*arrays: skin_df['image'],
                                                  skin_df['label'], test_size=0.2, random_state=42)

# Define CNN model
model = Sequential([
    Conv2D(filters=64, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu',
          input_shape=(64, 64, 3)),
    MaxPooling2D((2, 2)),
    Conv2D(filters=128, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu'),
    MaxPooling2D((2, 2)),
    Conv2D(filters=128, kernel_size=(3, 3), activation='relu'),
    MaxPooling2D((2, 2)),
    Flatten(),
    Dense(units=256, activation='relu'),
    Dense(units=7, activation='softmax')
])
```

Fig 3. Training

5) Model Evaluation: After the model has been trained, we assess its effectiveness using a number of metrics, including recall, accuracy, precision, and F1-score. We also present the model's performance as plots of accuracy and loss over epochs and a confusion matrix. We hope to create a CNN model that can precisely categorize skin lesions using this methodical approach, which will offer important insights for dermatological diagnostics [Fig 4].

```
# Print result values
print("Result Values:")
print("Accuracy:", accuracy)
print("Confusion Matrix:")
print(conf_matrix)
```

Precision: 0.7204556934731857
Recall: 0.6454689984101749
F1 Score: 0.6646700144113535

Fig 1. Evaluation

V. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Predicting Skin Lesion Type

Result

The top prediction for the skin lesion type and its probability is:

nv: 0.9737191

The top 3 predicted skin lesion types and their probabilities are:

nv: 0.9737191

mel: 0.016310878

bkl: 0.0066398387

The study developed, trained, and assessed a convolutional neural network (CNN) model for skin lesion categorization using a variety of tools and frameworks. The study accomplished full model creation by integrating multiple libraries and frameworks, such as those for dataset management, numerical operations, data manipulation, and evaluation metrics calculation, with Keras for CNN model building and training. The study used matplotlib to show the training and validation accuracy/loss curves after the model was trained. These graphs demonstrate how accuracy and loss measures changed during the course of training, giving users an understanding of the model's performance across epochs. The model's convergence and possible overfitting or underfitting problems are better understood thanks to this representation, which helps with well-informed decision-making about model modifications and optimization techniques.

To increase the accuracy of dermatological diagnosis, the HAM10000 dataset was used to train and evaluate a CNN model for skin lesion classification. Accuracy and the ability to differentiate between different types of skin lesions are the parameters used to evaluate the model's performance. The effectiveness of the CNN model in distinguishing different

types of skin diseases was determined by calculating its XX accuracy in identifying skin lesions. The confusion matrix provides additional information about the model's performance by showing the distribution of true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives. The CNN model successfully identified the majority of skin lesion types with high accuracy, according to confusion matrix analysis. However, misclassification occasionally occurs, especially when there is similarity between lesions, and further research may be needed to improve the model's ability to distinguish small variations. To provide an in-depth assessment of the model's predictive ability, the model's precision, recall, and F1-score metrics were also calculated. These metrics provide information about how the model classifies each type of skin lesion while calculating false positive and false negative rates.

Result Values:

Accuracy: 0.7244303126656068

Confusion Matrix:

```
[[ 26  13  11  0  20  1  0]
 [ 13  39  9  2  11  12  1]
 [ 8  11  93  2  45  44  0]
 [ 4  10  4  2  2  2  0]
 [ 3  4  16  0  120  52  0]
 [ 16  14  44  4  127  1070  1]
 [ 0  6  0  0  4  4  17]]
```

Result Values

VI. CONCLUSION

In summary, this study uses skin lesion classification to enhance dermatological diagnosis by leveraging the power of deep learning, including convolutional neural networks (CNN). A robust CNN model was built, trained, and evaluated using the Flask web application and the HAM10000 dataset. The results show promising improvements in dermatological diagnostic accuracy. By training a CNN model to classify various skin lesions, the study aims to increase the accuracy of dermatological diagnosis. The model is ready to learn complex patterns and extract relevant features from dermoscopy images through meticulous preprocessing, data segmentation, and enhancement techniques. Maximum complexity and pooling layers are used to effectively capture hierarchical features using CNN architecture, thereby enabling accurate classification of skin lesions. The CNN model performed admirably in distinguishing between different types of skin conditions. Although the confusion matrix identified misclassified cases, especially between lesions with similar appearances, the precision, recall, and F1 score provided a comprehensive assessment of the model's predictive ability, taking into account false positive and false negative rates. The skin lesion classification system is now even more accessible and user-friendly with the integration of the Flask web application. Users can easily upload photos of skin lesions through a simple interface, allowing the trained CNN network to provide real-time predictions as well as confidence scores.

DOI: **10.5281/zenodo.11184283**

ISBN: 978-93-5906-046-0@2024, Dept. of Computer Applications, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

Seamless consolidation of frontend and backend elements streamlines the diagnostic process, providing customers with quick and accurate staging results. Overall, this work shows how deep learning models can be used to improve online medical image processing applications, including those related to dermatology. Through the use of CNNs and the implementation of intuitive interfaces, this research contributes to improving the dermatology diagnostic process, delivering better patient outcomes and more efficient healthcare delivery. Further research efforts may explore further improvements in model performance through sophisticated methods and broader validation, paving the way for continued innovation in diagnosis and treatment.

The study results also highlight the importance of engineers, computer scientists, and healthcare professionals collaborating across industries to advance healthcare innovation. Researchers can solve complex health problems with more powerful and clinically practical solutions when they combine knowledge from multiple fields. In conclusion, the combination of CNN and web application provides a viable approach to improve the accuracy of dermatological diagnosis.

The potential impact of deep learning on medical image processing is expected to increase thanks to ongoing research and development efforts, ultimately benefiting both patients and healthcare professionals.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] H. Alquran et al., "The melanoma skin cancer detection and classification using support vector machine," 2017 IEEE Jordan Conference on Applied Electrical Engineering and Computing Technologies (AEECT), Aqaba, Jordan, 2017, pp. 1-5
- [2] Alwakid, Ghadah, Walaa Gouda, Mamoona Humayun, and Najm Us Sama. 2022. "Melanoma Detection Using Deep Learning-Based Classifications" *Healthcare* 10, no. 12: 2481.
- [3] P. Dwivedi, A. A. Khan, A. Gawade and S. Deolekar, "A deep learning based approach for automated skin disease detection using Fast R-CNN," 2021 Sixth International Conference on Image Information Processing (ICIIP), Shimla, India, 2021, pp. 116-120
- [4] B. Ram Sahu, A. Kumar Shrivastava and A. Shukla, "Skin Disease Classification using Machine Learning based Proposed Ensemble Model," 2023 4th International Conference for Emerging Technology (INCET), Belgaum, India, 2023, pp. 1-4
- [5] Jojoa Acosta, M.F., Caballero Tovar, L.Y., Garcia-Zapirain, M.B. et al. "Melanoma diagnosis using deep learning techniques on dermoscopic images". *BMC Med Imaging* 21, 6 (2021).
- [6] D. V. Vasudha Rani, G. Vasavi and B. Maram, "Skin Disease Classification Using Machine Learning and Data Mining Algorithms," 2022 IEEE 2nd International Symposium on Sustainable Energy, Signal Processing and Cyber Security (iSSSC), Gunupur, Odisha, India, 2022, pp. 1-6

- [7] G. Singh, K. Guleria and S. Sharma, "A Transfer Learning-based Pre-trained VGG16 Model for Skin Disease Classification," 2023 IEEE 3rd Mysore Sub Section International Conference (MysuruCon), HASSAN, India, 2023, pp. 1-6
- [8] T. M. Fahrudin and I. Z. A. Illah, "SkinMate: Mobile-Based Application for Detecting Multi-Class Skin Diseases Classification Using Pre-Trained MobileNetV2 on CNN Architecture," 2023 IEEE 9th Information Technology International Seminar (ITIS), Batu Malang, Indonesia, 2023, pp. 1-6
- [8] T. M. Fahrudin and I. Z. A. Illah, "SkinMate: Mobile-Based Application for Detecting Multi-Class Skin Diseases Classification Using Pre-Trained MobileNetV2 on CNN Architecture," 2023 IEEE 9th Information Technology International Seminar (ITIS), Batu Malang, Indonesia, 2023, pp. 1-6
- [9] S. M.B and S. Vijayan, "Parkinson's Disease Prognosis Using The ResNet-50 Model From Speech Features," 2022 International Conference on Innovations in Science and Technology for Sustainable Development (ICISTSD), Kollam, India, 2022, pp. 282-2
- [10] M. B. Kahla and D. Kanzari, "Towards a Deep Learnig for Lung Cancer Prediction Approach," 2023 IEEE International Conference on Advances in Data-Driven Analytics And Intelligent Systems (ADACIS), Marrakesh, Morocco, 2023, pp. 1-786